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Thu, Feb 1, 2024 at 9:30 AM

To: ccpgrrom@gmail.com

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Dear Dr. Graña,

It is with regret that we must inform you that your following submission to Preprints has been declined for announcement. We have some concerns about the content and that it doesn't fit with the guidelines we apply for posted preprints. In such cases, we prefer to take a cautious approach and recommend that you submit it to a journal for a more thorough evaluation. I wish you all the best with eventual publication of this paper.

Preprints ID: preprints-97878

Type: Brief Report

Title: A critical reading of "COVID-19 Prediction Using Black-Box Based Pearson Correlation Approach"

Authors: Manuel Graña, Goizalde Badiola-Zabala, Guillermo Cano-Escalera

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Submission received: 2024-01-31

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If you have any questions, please contact us at info@preprints.org.

Best Regards,
Ivana Jelisavcic
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